

Oxidation of some Disubstituted Diphenyl Sulphoxides with Sodium *N*-Bromobenzene Sulphonamide in Presence of Mercury(II). A Kinetic and Mechanistic Study

G. MANGALAM* and SUBBIAH MEENAKSHI SUNDARAM

Department of Technology, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 002

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Kinetics of bromamine-B (BAB) oxidation of some *p*- and *p'*-disubstituted sulphoxides, to give the corresponding sulphones, have been studied in aqueous acetic acid medium. A first order dependence on the concentration of each reactant was observed. Rate data showed an inverse dependence on [benzene sulphonamide] and a fractional order in [H⁺]. The reactions are little affected by the addition of Hg^{II}, ruling out the catalytic role. A negative ρ value suggests the sulphur becoming electron-deficient in the transition state. The rate-limiting step involves the interaction of the substrate and [H₂OBr⁺] species.

BAB is used as an oxidimetric titrant in direct potentiometric and visual end point titrations¹. BAB is reduced to benzenesulphonamide. *N*-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) and *N*-bromoacetamide (NBA) oxidations of organic compounds are complicated by bromine oxidation, which can be obviated using Hg^{II}². In some reactions involving NBS and NBA, Hg^{II} also plays a catalytic role³. But no such interesting observation has yet been recorded in the reactions of bromamine-B. These mechanistic features led us to investigate the title reaction.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry (1 : 1) of the oxidation was determined with varying amounts of oxidant in excess over the substrate,

The plot of k_1 versus [sulphoxide] ($r=0.998$) gives straight line that passes through the origin, indicating the rate of oxidation to have a first-order dependence on sulphoxide. This is further demonstrated by the constancy of k_2 values (Table 1). The kinetic data indicate a first order dependence with respect to the oxidant as known from the linearity of the rate profiles. The inverse dependence of the rate on [BBA] (Table 1) may probably be ascribed to the equilibrium of BAB with a less reactive species i.e. its dimer or *N,N*-dibromobenzenesulphonamide⁴.

The rate data at different solvent compositions and ionic strength (Table 2) show the involvement of an ion and a neutral molecule in the reaction. The inverse dependence of the reaction rate on [benzenesulphonamide] suggests the formation of the product along with the reactive species in an equilibrium step prior to the rate-limiting step.

The reaction was carried out with varying concentrations of perchloric acid keeping other variables constant and maintaining the ionic strength constant (Table 3). The log-log plot of k_1 versus [H⁺] results in a straight line with a gradient 0.48 ($r=0.990$).

TABLE 1—RATE DATA FOR OXIDATION

[Hg^{II}]= 1.96×10^{-3} M, [HOAc]=60% (v/v), $I=0.14$ M, [HClO₄]= 2.78×10^{-1} M, $T_{emp.}=35^\circ$

10^3 [BAB] M	10^2 [Sulphoxide] M	$10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^2 k_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.7	2.8	14.34	
1.1	2.8	8.54	
1.4	2.8	6.04	
2.1	2.8	4.68	
2.8	2.8	4.01	
1.4	1.4	3.07	2.18
1.4	2.8	6.04	2.14
1.4	3.4	7.04	2.08
1.4	3.9	7.97	2.02
1.4	4.5	9.09	2.02
1.4	5.6	11.70	2.08

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH AND PRODUCT

[Sulphoxide]= 2.80×10^{-2} M, [HOAc]=60% (v/v), [BAB]= 1.40×10^{-3} M, [Hg^{II}]= 1.96×10^{-3} M, [HClO₄]= 2.78×10^{-1} M, $T_{emp.}=35^\circ$

10^2 [NaClO ₄] M	10^3 [BSA] M	$10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹
—	—	5.60
3.5	—	5.76
14.0	—	6.04
28.0	—	7.57
42.0	—	8.03
81.0	—	11.97
14.0 ^a	—	5.13
14.0 ^b	—	6.48
14.0 ^c	—	7.20
14.0	0.62	4.47
14.0	1.15	3.59
14.0	1.87	2.71
14.0	2.49	2.31

^a50% HOAc (v/v), ^b65% HOAc (v/v), ^c70% HOAc (v/v)

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [H⁺]

[Sulphoxide] = 2.80 × 10⁻² M, [Hg^{II}] = 1.96 × 10⁻³ M, [BAB] = 1.40 × 10⁻³ M, [HOAc] = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 35°

10 ² [HClO ₄] M	10 ³ [NaClO ₄] M	10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
4.30	37.50	3.36
6.95	34.85	3.69
13.90	27.90	4.93
27.80	14.00	6.04
41.80	—	8.04

Mercuric acetate is introduced to trap the bromide ions. Though in many cases, catalytic role of Hg^{II} has been reported³, in the present study Hg^{II} has no effect on the rate of oxidation and the rate remains practically unaffected (Table 4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF Hg^{II}

[Sulphoxide] = 2.80 × 10⁻² M, [HOAc] = 60% (v/v), [BAB] = 1.40 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 2.78 × 10⁻¹ M, I = 0.14 M, Temp. = 35°

10 ³ [Hg ^{II}] M	10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
1.47	6.64
1.96	6.04
2.45	6.49
2.94	6.01
3.92	6.06

An insight into the nature of the transition state can be gained from an analysis of the substituent effects. The effect of substituents on the rate of oxidation has been studied by employing a number of *p*- and *p'*-disubstituted sulphoxides. From the results it is evident that electron-releasing substituents accelerate the rate and electron-withdrawing ones retard the rate of the reaction (Table 5).

TABLE 5—RATE DATA ON SUBSTITUTED SULPHOXIDES

[BAB] = 1.40 × 10⁻³ M, [Hg^{II}] = 1.96 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 2.78 × 10⁻¹ M, I = 0.14 M, [HOAc] = 70% (v/v)

Sl. no.	Substituent	10 ² k ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)		
		25°	35°	45°
1.	H	0.96	2.56	6.21
2.	4,4'-Me	2.95	8.53	17.28
3.	4,4'-Cl	0.21	0.40	0.88
4.	4,4'-Br	0.13	0.24	0.49
5.	4,4'-NO ₂	0.01	0.02	0.03

Activation enthalpy and entropy values for the oxidation process have been computed from the rate data measured at three temperatures (Table 6). The plot of log k₂ (35°) versus log k₂ (25°) gives a straight line with r = 0.998. The excellent correlation indicates that all the substituted compounds investigated follow a common mechanism.

Applying the Hammett equation the ρ value was determined from the plot of log k₂ vs 2σ.

TABLE 6—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Sl. no.	Substituent	ΔG [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹ (308 K)	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	r	SD
1.	H	85.0	70.9	45.7	0.999	0.012
2.	4,4'-Me	82.1	66.9	49.5	0.995	0.124
3.	4,4'-Cl	89.5	54.6	113.5	0.998	0.068
4.	4,4'-Br	90.9	49.0	135.9	0.998	0.053
5.	4,4'-NO ₂	98.1	54.9	140.3	0.998	0.062

The ρ value of -1.44 suggests that the sulphur becomes electron-deficient in the rate-limiting step. This is in agreement with the well documented nucleophilic role of the sulphides in several oxidations⁶.

Mechanism and rate law:

In acid solution, anion picks up a proton to give the free acid, RNHBr⁶,

Although the free acid has not been isolated, as in the case of the corresponding chloro compound, its formation in acid solutions can be visualised.

The order with respect to oxidant is unity may dissuade the possibility of RNBr₂ being the active species.

$$\text{Rate} = k_5 [\text{SO}] [\text{H}_2\text{OBr}^+]$$

Substituting the value of [H₂OBr⁺] leads to the rate law,

$$\frac{-d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = \frac{k_3 K_2 K_1 [\text{SO}] [\text{BAB}]_0 [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{RNH}_2] \{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_1' [\text{BAB}]_0\}}$$

where, K'₂ = K₂[H₂O]

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_3 K_2 K_1 [\text{SO}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{RNH}_2] \{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_1' [\text{BAB}]_0\}}$$

This rate equation explains the observed orders with respect to substrate, oxidant, H⁺ and also

accounts for the inverse dependence on the product and oxidant.

Experimental

All the sulphoxides were recrystallised before use and the purity was checked from physical constants. An aqueous solution of the oxidant was standardised iodometrically. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. The ionic strength of the medium was maintained constant. The reactions were performed under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of sulphoxide over BAB.

The rate of disappearance of the oxidant was followed by the iodometric estimation of the unreacted BAB⁷. Computations of the rate constants were made from the plot of log titre versus time. All rate constants are the average of two or more determinations. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants and activation parameters obtained agreed within $\pm 2\%$.

Product analysis: The reaction mixtures containing excess BAB were kept aside at kinetic temperature for 48 h. Then it was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with a saturated solution of NaCl containing 1% NaOH to remove benzenesulphonamide and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solid obtained on removal of ether was crystallised from ethanol, m.p.

126°. The m.p. of its mixture with an authentic sample of diphenyl sulphone was not depressed. Tlc of diphenyl sulphone showed identical behaviour of the oxidation product and an authentic sample.

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